

Updated Handbook for System Administrators

Handbook for System Administrators: Specification of a standard recommendation for an ESM System Software Stack

Deliverable D3.6

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1. Abstract /publishable summary

Nowadays, to build, run and configure up-to-date weather and climate models takes many more components than just the source codes. Models are subject to a long list of dependencies in the form of libraries, open source and/or commercial software packages or many other pieces of software to be available to the users such as system utilities. These requirements make the life of system administrators in HPC centres hard. When a new user gets resources on a specific platform, it will take time before the actual simulations can start, because platform related problems with models and software need to be solved first.

This deliverable provides a recommended methodology to select, configure and install a complete ESM software stack in the form of a handbook. This handbook is intended to ease the deployment of models and to reduce the time to start simulations at an HPC facility both informing the scientists and the HPC systems administrators. The time to solution from idea to published result should thus be substantially reduced. Ideally, following the guidelines in this document, the centres willing to run weather and climate models will be prepared to offer all the tools required by these models, and their users, the scientists.

For clarity, in this document we do not define the software stack needed for a centre to run weather and climate models. This definition comes from the deliverable D3.1¹.

D3.6 is an update of the D3.5 deliverable. This current version of the handbook reviews, completes and refactors the first version of the document. A clearer section with requirements distributed by topics has been added and the work done with automated software management has been moved into the last section.

2. Conclusion & Results

The main result of the deliverable is the publication of the next version of the *Handbook for System Administrators: Specification of a standard recommendation for an ESM System Software Stack*. This version will be available on the ESIWACE website www.esiwace.eu. It is the final version supported from ESIWACE.

The handbook contains:

- Revised requirements that ESM workflows pose to HPC environments, as well as recommendations and best practices to fulfil them;
- A list of the system software that is common for ESM workflows;
- A description of tools that allow for automation of the system software deployment.

3. Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of all the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Description of Action:

¹ ESIWACE Application Software Framework: A White Paper. Version 1: Specification of a Standard Recommendation for an End-to-end Workflows and Application Software Environments Framework

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable?
Improve the efficiency and productivity of numerical weather and climate simulation on high-performance computing platforms	Yes
Support the end-to-end workflow of global Earth system modelling for weather and climate simulation in high performance computing environments	Yes
The European weather and climate science community will drive the governance structure that defines the services to be provided by ESIWACE	No
Foster the interaction between industry and the weather and climate community on the exploitation of high-end computing systems, application codes and services.	Yes
Increase competitiveness and growth of the European HPC industry	Yes

Specific goals in the workplan	Contribution of this deliverable?
Provide services to the user community that will impact beyond the lifetime of the project.	Yes
Improve scalability and shorten the time-to-solution for climate and operational weather forecasts at increased resolution and complexity to be run on future extreme-scale HPC systems.	Yes
Foster usability of the available tools, software, computing and data handling infrastructures.	Yes
Pursue exploitability of climate and weather model results.	Yes
Establish governance of common software management to avoid unnecessary and redundant development and to deliver the best available solutions to the user community.	Yes
Provide open access to research results and open source software at international level.	Yes
Exploit synergies with other relevant activities and projects and also with the global weather and climate community	Yes

4. Detailed report on the deliverable

The Handbook for system administrators: Specification of a standard recommendation for an ESM System Software Stack is contained in the Annex 1 to this deliverable.

5. References (Bibliography)

- Petar Forai, Kenneth Hoste, Guilherme Peretti-Pezzi, Brett Bode 2016. [Making Scientific Software Installation Reproducible On Cray Systems Using EasyBuild](#). In *Proceedings of the Cray User Group 2016* (CUG'2016).
- Markus Geimer, Kenneth Hoste, and Robert McLay. 2014. [Modern scientific software management using EasyBuild and Lmod](#). In *Proceedings of the First International Workshop on HPC User Support Tools* (HUST '14). IEEE Press, Piscataway, NJ, USA, 41-51. DOI=<http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/HUST.2014.8>
- Kenneth Hoste, Jens Timmerman, Andy Georges, and Stijn De Weirdt. 2012. [EasyBuild: Building Software with Ease](#). In *Proceedings of the 2012 SC Companion: High Performance Computing, Networking Storage and Analysis* (SCC '12). IEEE Computer Society, Washington, DC, USA, 572-582. DOI=<http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/SC.Companion.2012.81>
- Todd Gamblin, Matthew P. LeGendre, Michael R. Collette, Gregory L. Lee, Adam Moody, Bronis R. de Supinski, and W. Scott Futral. The Spack Package Manager: Bringing Order to HPC Software Chaos. In *Supercomputing 2015 (SC'15)*, Austin, Texas, November 15-20 2015. LLNL-CONF-669890.
- 5th ENES Workshop on High Performance Computing for High-resolution Climate and Weather Modelling, Lecce, May 2018. [abstracts](#)

6. Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Dissemination

Materials for the public and the audiences beyond the ESIWACE project is disseminated with the publication on the ESIWACE website and is advertised in ESIWACE presentations and publications.

The attached Handbook will be updated regularly. Information about the updates will be disseminated through the regular channels: project webpages, workshops and citations.

6.2 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

X	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

7. The delivery is delayed: Yes No

8. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

9. Sustainability

9.1. Lessons learnt: both positive and negative that can be drawn from the experiences of the work to date

A culture of cooperation between the centres, quite clear setting for the goals, and good understanding for the usefulness of the approach has aided the development of this handbook.

9.2 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

This deliverable will take as input the list of software defined by D3.1.

Links with other WPs: The models used up to now for deploying the methodology are models used in the Scalability WP2. In this sense, the work done is expected to be very useful for the other partners.

Concerning WP1, we plan to interact strongly on the list of community software and the list of tools used to install and configure the software stack. In addition, the list will be communicated to PRACE and Tier0 and Tier1 centres.

10. Dissemination activities

Type of dissemination and communication activities	Details	Location , dates	Audience	Zenodo record / link to website	Estimated number of persons reached
Participation to a conference	PRACE Days 2017: Kim Serradell, Sergey Kosukhin. Presentation "Software stack deployment for Earth System Modelling using Spack"	15-18 May 2017, Barcelona (ES)	Scientific Community (higher education, Research)	https://events.prace-ri.eu/event/575/	100
Training	ARM DDT debugger training for Earth System Modellers at BSC	6 March 2018, Barcelona (ES)	Scientific Community (higher education, Research)	-	20
Participation to a workshop	Sergey Kosukhin (MPI-M), Presentation "Spack for ICON, Current status" at the ICON infrastructure meeting	8-9 March 2018, Karlsruhe (DE)	Scientific Community (higher education, Research)	10.5281/zenodo.1344554	15

Participation to a workshop	Sergey Kosukhin (MPI-M), , Presentation “Software Stack Deployment for Earth System Modelling using Spack” at the ESIWACE General Assembly	12-13 December 2017, Berlin (DE)	Scientific Community (higher education, Research)	10.5281/zenodo.1344560	30
Participation to a workshop	Sergey Kosukhin (MPI-M), Kim Serradell (BSC), Reinhard Budich (MPI-M), Presentation „Software Stack Deployment for Earth System Modelling“at the DKRZ User Workshop,	9-10 October 2017, Hamburg (DE)	Scientific Community (higher education, Research)	10.5281/zenodo.1344562	50

Handbook for System Administrators (and Users)

A Living Document on the Specification of a Standard Recommendation for an ESM System Software Stack

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1. Introduction

This document provides guidelines for system administrators and advanced users to support their efforts in preparation of supercomputing environments for Earth System Modelling (ESM) experiments. Along with the general recommendations on system configuration, this document contains information on the system software stack that is common and required for most ESM workflows.

It also traces our research on better and easier ways to build a complete software stack for the Earth System community. We do not only present our solutions but also the approaches that we have discarded for various reasons.

The document is structured as follows: a list gathering all the topics that a system administrator should consider when dealing with ESMs is followed by a description of how we implemented automatic and reproducible installations using existing tools, and a final section is provided with conclusions and an outlook.

We also want this document to become a starting point for collaboration between users and system administrators. This is reflected in the title, which changed for this update. The former are expected to refer to this document to get indications on what problems need to be solved and what questions need to be posed to fill the gap between the system software stack that is available on the system they use and the (modelling) software stack that is necessary to run their experiments. The latter are asked to check out our recommendations and help improve this handbook where useful.

It should be noted that HPC environments can be configured following very different approaches and usage policies, thus not all the recommendations presented might be applicable to all particular cases. This document will be kept updated over the next years, which means that some solutions presented here can evolve or get discarded over time.

2. Requirements for ESMs

In the first version of the handbook, we provided some requirements for system administrators based on our experiences working with different clusters and ESMs. These requirements were not organised under sections and it was not always easy to follow and read. Based on the experiences we gained during the reporting period and a useful panel discussion on computing and data centre support for weather and climate models and workflows held in the 5th ENES HPC Workshop, we decided to rename the handbook (see above). And we gathered a list of key topics for the community and adapted it to the handbook. In the following sections, we will list each of these topics and make recommendations and propose best practices. The list is organised from generic machine topics to specific ones affecting ESMs. We start with environment setup and system software; then we cover different hardware topics related to HPC, to finally conclude with libraries and how to do an automatic compilation using tools.

a) Environment

The best way to enable users to adjust software environments to their needs is to install and configure a flexible environment. Different solutions are available in the market, but we will present and discuss Lmod, a New Environment Module System¹. Lmod is increasingly used and deployed in new clusters due its flexibility, ease of use and ease of configuration.

The Environment Modules package provides for the dynamic modification of a user's environment via module files. Each module file contains the information needed to configure the shell for an application. Once the module package is initialised, the environment can be modified on a per-module basis using the module command which interprets module files.

Typically, module files instruct the module command to alter or set shell environment variables such as PATH, MANPATH, etc. Modules can be loaded and unloaded dynamically and atomically, in a clean fashion. Modules are useful in managing different versions of applications. Modules can also be bundled into meta-modules that will load an entire suite of different applications. In addition, modules can manage incompatibilities and prevent modules from being loaded if an environment conflict would result.

There are different strategies to organise modules. Some system administrators use a tag-based system, creating categories as system, tools, libraries, data, visualisation, etc. This strategy can be useful to the user but has two main disadvantages: the number of categories can grow, depending on the fine grain classification, and some packages are hard to classify and could be installed in more than one category.

Based on BSC experience (and following what SPACK does by default when creating modules), we recommend another classification based on the architecture of the machine (see also section “LMod hierarchical module files” in SPACK documentation³). Many of the research

¹ <http://lmod.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

³ https://spack.readthedocs.io/en/latest/module_file_support.html

centres have more than one HPC cluster sharing the same environment. Having a folder structure based on architectures and operating systems (Figure 1) can greatly simplify dealing with a complex infrastructure.


```
bsc32353@p9login1:~  
bsc32353@p9login1:~ 112x37  
[bsc32353@PW9:p9login1 ~]$ module av  
----- /gpfs/projects/bsc32/software/rhel/7.4/ppc64le/POWER9/modules/all -----  
ANTLR/2.7.7-foss-2018b-Python-2.7.15      Qt5/5.5.1-foss-2018b  
Autoconf/2.69-GCCcore-7.3.0              R/3.5.0-foss-2018b  
Automake/1.16.1-GCCcore-7.3.0           ROOT/v5.34.38-foss-2018b-Python-2.7.15  
Autotools/20180311-GCCcore-7.3.0       Ruby/2.5.0-foss-2018b  
Bison/3.0.4-GCCcore-7.3.0              SQLite/3.23.0-GCCcore-7.3.0  
Bison/3.0.4                             ScaLAPACK/2.0.2-gompi-2018b-OpenBLAS-0.3.0  
Bison/3.0.5                             ScaLAPACK/2.0.2-gompi-2018b-OpenBLAS-0.3.1 (D)  
Boost/1.66.0-foss-2018b-Python-2.7.15  Shapely/1.6.4.post2-foss-2018b-Python-2.7.15  
CDFT00LS/3.0a8-foss-2018b              Szzip/2.1.1-GCCcore-7.3.0  
CD0/1.6.3-foss-2018b                   Tcl/8.6.8-GCCcore-7.3.0 (D)  
CD0/1.8.2-foss-2018b                   Tk/8.6.8-GCCcore-7.3.0  
CD0/1.9.4-foss-2018b                   Tkinter/2.7.15-foss-2018b-Python-2.7.15
```

Figure 1: Module installation based on /distro/version/arch/machine

b) System Software

Our experience shows that it is often hard to strictly distinguish between application software, which is expected to be handled by users, and system software, which should be deployed and maintained by system administrators of an HPC facility (see Figure 2). In the scope of this document we define *application software* as software that users directly work with and *system software* as software that users do not have to know about but which is essential for their workflows and is also not too domain-specific to expect a system administrator to be ready to maintain it.

Depending on many factors (e.g. the primary scientific domain, hardware architecture, operating system, etc.), supercomputing facilities have different policies on what software is available to their users by default, and approaches to how that is implemented. It should be also noted that the default software stack often contains custom optimised versions of the commonly used libraries. This has to be considered during the application deployment process. That is why users should be provided with a common point, from which they can start working with an HPC system. This point could be a web-based set of Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ) or a complete User Guide.

For ESMs, a good practice is having the models (if it's a common model well known and used by the community) already installed and built appropriately for the infrastructure (using the most suitable compilers and flags to get the best performance possible) in the common software folders. Not all ESMs exhibit the same degree of sensitivity to HPC configuration; some of them are not dependent on the configuration, and in such cases one build satisfies all needs. This central installation can also provide standard submission infrastructure and test jobs to make the deployment easier and safer for the user.

The SW-Stacks

1st ESIWACE Review, 08.04.2016

Figure 2: Application and system software stacks

c) Queues and job policy

In this section, we will describe the schedulers deployed by the partners and use their experiences to recommend a configuration for an ESM environment.

Different schedulers are on the market. There are commercial and free solutions. We will compare the usage of a commercial one (LSF from IBM) with a free open source solution, SLURM. The recommendations below are based on the experience of the Earth System department at Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC), where the HPC system Mare Nostrum is used in both operational and research mode.

Testbed partitions

ESM models are complex pieces of software that are sensitive to many factors. They typically require a significant degree of tuning in order to develop optimal scientific and computational configurations to capture desired physical processes and to maximise efficient throughput. In a development environment, users need fast turnaround, testing and tuning need to select appropriate compiler options, processor decomposition, load balancing, pre- and post-processing workflows, etc. For this purpose, it is recommended to provide users with small partitions that allow allocation of only a few nodes for a short period but have high priority. This enables intensive and timely testing to be undertaken prior to running the experiments in production.

Task prioritisation

A common practice for ESM workflow implementation is to split simulation periods into smaller chunks (usually from one to ten years of model time) and submit them to the scheduler as sequential jobs. The main reason for this is to keep the job chains running in case of hardware or software failures (that are expected to become rather the rule than exception at exascale), and to prevent wasting significant amounts of CPU time that otherwise would be necessary to rerun calculations from the initial state. This approach also allows a straightforward solution to running post-processing tasks simultaneously with the model and thus enhances parallelism. To support this well-established practice, it is highly recommended to adjust job scheduling rules to allow for repetitive job submissions from the same user by disabling possible priority penalties. Ideally, if one job is finished the next one that appears in the job queue within a minute should get the released resources⁴.

Operational runs

Operational forecasting runs are configured to start in specific time and cannot afford waiting times in queues. To ensure the availability of resources, reservations are created depending on a user, amount of resources, start, and wall-clock time.

When dealing with this kind of setups, BSC experience favours SLURM rather than LSF. LSF showed many issues e.g. with reservations when enabling system maintenance. SLURM has proven to be much more reliable in BSC's experience, which is mandatory for this kind of configuration. Furthermore, SLURM has a wider community and consequently, BSC has found it easier to get support in case of trouble.

Following these operational requirements, there is a branch of ESM which deals with extreme events: hurricanes, fires or tsunamis, among many others. Models for these applications are usually run in research mode to develop and tune the model. However, when such configurations are validated and prepared for operational forecasting, they need to be ready to run when an extreme event happens. This is what we call urgent computing: decision making during extreme events based on simulations. These simulations need to be run in a short-term to provide results as soon as possible to decision makers and responders. Procedures to give resources (using scheduler reservation) urgently need to be established well before the events, to be able to react in time. This includes user setups, high priority queues, and access.

Job Monitoring

Some HPC users are experienced users: they have been developing codes or they have accumulated a lot of experience after running thousands of simulations. They know the codes much better than system administrators do and their knowledge can be very valuable to debug the codes and search for errors or malfunctions. For this reason, system administrators must allow these users to monitor their simulations during the simulations, but also after the runs. Accessing the job scheduler information or having some interface based on systems like Ganglia

⁴ This recommendation is implemented e.g. at DKRZ

or others, can improve the productivity of their daily activity. This includes general information from the run, but also hardware counter information⁵.

For less experienced users of HPC systems, a monitoring system for the simulation (based on scientific results) should also be deployed. Monitoring execution time of a simulation and stopping it, if the user detects that there is an error, can save time for the user, and computing resources.

Node Types

To cover all ESM HPC needs, a heterogeneous cluster can be designed to handle various tasks with optimised performance, such as pre- and post-processing. Before and after the simulation stage, some tasks, usually requiring high bandwidth for the I/O both to memory and storage, need to be completed. Providing the user with such a facility with improved performance w.r.t these specific tasks can only increase the efficiency of the user's final workflow.

In order to access login nodes, SSH (preferably without port numbers) is the most suitable method. Depending on the security level of the organisation, other requirements can be deployed (like cryptocards). Bear in mind, these extra security constraints can have an impact when trying to set workflow manager tools or similar mechanisms.

We recommend providing users with information on the mechanisms of job submission. Commands for job submission and control should be easily identified and explained (in the machine user guide).

If the cluster has dedicated service nodes, whose architecture differs from the actual compute nodes (configuration not recommended), this should be indicated to the user. Build procedures can differ when using these nodes and compilation scripts have to be modified to reflect the differences.

Login nodes should have input and output network access. Restricting output traffic for security reasons can have a strong impact on the user, increasing the complexity in his daily work. Without network output access, the deployment software procedure explained in the third section gets more complicated and accessing software development tools (such as a gitlab server) can be difficult and tedious. Limiting network access can also impact software or tools requiring a license server to connect.

Sysadmins need to also allow processes to be launched manually from the command line (e.g. for debugging purposes). The most convenient method of obtaining a set of nodes for interactive use is requesting an interactive session to the scheduler. This request can be obtained with queueing commands but we recommend to set up a wrapper to reduce the complexity of the command to execute. In this sense, the "sinteractive" script⁶ is a great example. The only concern of this type of allocation is to avoid granting big wall clock times: users often forget that the session is open and consume resources until the time limit is

⁵ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hardware_performance_counter

⁶ <https://github.com/jabl/sinteractive>

reached. On the other hand, to discourage users to use the login nodes to run computations affecting other users, we recommend to add system checks to limit CPU time in login nodes.

To allow users to easily transfer output from simulations, login nodes need to sustain certain download/upload transfer speeds to input and output files. For typical climate workloads, our experience with many machines around the world show that a of minimum 100 Mb/s typically suffices (1Gb/s recommended). If there is not enough network bandwidth, the user will spend much time to monitor transfers and, consequently, have the impression of wasting time. To ensure this connection standard, system administrators can create dedicated transfer nodes with different techniques and services to transfer data.

Finally, login nodes need to provide the ability to run services for suite management like Cylc or any other management workflow tool. ESM workflows are more and more complex, therefore tools to run these simulations have to be deployed. Sometimes, these tools have specific system requirements (open ports, daemons running in the login nodes...) that don't follow administration policies in the facilities. Discussions between users and sysadmins, to explain the implications and needs are mandatory to overcome and bypass these restrictions.

d) Storage

ESM experiments produce voluminous data sets. Increases in resolution, number of model components, number of variables and ensemble sizes all contribute to an increase in data volume needed to perform experiments. The following recommendations, adapted to ESM simulations, will make better use of the storage. In this analysis, we identify three different kinds of storage, used for different stages of the simulation, where each one has different policies.

- **Fast storage:** The place where output of the simulation is stored in. This filesystem is intended to quickly store model simulation results and move them as soon as possible to a storage dedicated to post-processing. In this case, it is best practice to implement an automatic purge of files not used after a defined time. This can have a critical impact on inexperienced users but ensures a better usage of storage. This filesystem needs to be fast, reliable and scalable, and maintained very well by both users and sysadmins.
- **Post-processing storage:** during, or shortly after the simulation, output (or a selection of output) is moved from the scratch simulation storage space to this partition for analysis and exploitation to generate scientific results. In this stage, usually conversion of file types, computation of new indexes or statistical analysis is applied. These operations are usually I/O intensive and should benefit from high-speed storage devices.
- **Long-term storage:** After the simulation has been post-processed, the results extracted and often published by the scientists, results need to be stored for some years to be accessed again if revision is needed. In this case, instant access is not needed: therefore, tapes are a good solution here.

Another recommendation related to storage is to have the different storage systems accessible from all available platforms. This interoperability is technically a bit harder to achieve, and as

such, needs to be well planned, configured and maintained. Nevertheless, it has tremendous benefit for the workflow of the users.

Shared filesystems (e.g. Lustre, GPFS, BeeGFS) are a key infrastructure for ESM users. In this document, we will skip any recommendation about disk sizes and volumes, but we will go into the disk requirements for ESM needs. ESM models themselves produce a vast amount of raw data, which often becomes a bottleneck of the whole workflow. The following post-processing, which usually takes place immediately after a model run (or simultaneously) reduces the amount of data that actually need to be stored for further analysis. Given that, a typical ESM workflow can significantly benefit from the availability of a low-latency partition, which would be used for short-term storage of the raw output of the model. If such storage is available on a machine, we recommend to explicitly inform the users about this and to invest into teaching them how to work with it, because this would foster the productivity of their research campaigns and potentially reduce the amount of computational resources they spend. It should be noted though, that I/O procedures, implemented in the versions of models and tools that are currently used, require the storage system to support POSIX.

ESM workflows are usually very sensitive to I/O configuration and this becomes critical for high-resolution runs. Fine-tuning of file system parameters and components is a key to productive computational experiments, and system administrators have to have deep and actual knowledge of the technologies deployed at their site.

e) Interconnects

Today's ESMs are very dependent on high-bandwidth, high throughput and low-latency interconnects to efficiently run over parallel programming models and to move data among the various nodes of a cluster. In this sense, a robust and performant interconnect is key part of the HPC infrastructure.

Well-known network products like Mellanox, OPA or Aries are a good choice. Similar to the storage section, ESMs are very sensitive to network configurations, so a strong knowledge or at least an intensive communication with the manufacturer's user support is needed.

Finally, the network in the system will most likely be broken up (physically or virtually with VLANs) into separate networks to serve different usages and isolate traffic.

f) Compilers

C and Fortran compilers are required for most ESM software. We recommend providing users with several compilers from different vendors (GNU, Intel, Supplier-specific, etc.) to allow for workarounds that might be necessary if a particular piece of software does not work when compiled with one of them. This approach of providing users with different choices should also be applied to the compiler versions and optimally complemented by support procedures in case of, e.g., compiler errors. Some codes do not run correctly with some specific version of a

compiler. System administrators should update (but also preserve) versions of the same compiler, and make older versions accessible.

We strongly recommend configuring compilers using environment modules. The user will be able to identify all the compilers and versions available on the system and will not have to take care of the many variables defined by compilers.

It is very important to make sure that it is possible to run the executables compiled with the compilers without loading the corresponding environment modules. In particular this means that the paths to the directories with the standard libraries of a compiler are injected as RPATHs into the executables at the linking stage. For example, GNU C/C++ compilers do not do this by default. This can be solved by employing the specs feature of the compilers⁷. See the following sequence of commands for reference:

```
#!/bin/bash
# Path to the installation directory of the compiler
GCC_PREFIX=./gcc-6.2.0
# Determining the absolute path to the compiler
gcc_prefix_abs=$(cd "$GCC_PREFIX"; pwd)
# The absolute path to the compiler
gcc_exe="$gcc_prefix_abs/bin/gcc"
# Determining the expected path to the spec file
specs_file=$(strace "$gcc_exe" 2>&1 | sed -n 's%^access("\(.specs\).%\1%p' | head -1)
# Dumping the default spec
"$gcc_exe" -dumpspecs > "$specs_file"
# Instructing the linker to inject the RPATH to the directory with the standard
# libraries when making a non-static linking
echo "*link: + %!static:-rpath $gcc_prefix_abs/lib64}" >> "$specs_file"
# Adding an empty line to the end of the spec file following its format
echo >> "$specs_file"
```

To inject RPATHs when linking with Intel compilers, configuration files⁸ can be used.

On Linux systems, most of the proprietary compilers, e.g. Intel, PGI, or NAG, rely on GCC and GNU Binutils. For example, Intel and PGI compilers use header and library files of the GCC implementation of the C++ Standard Library. Often, the default system versions of GCC and GNU Binutils installed at an HPC facility are too old to support the recent standards of the programming languages and modern processor architectures. This makes it mandatory to allow users to run proprietary compilers with the versions of GCC and GNU Binutils that meet their needs. For example, Intel compilers run the executables of GCC and GNU Binutils available in the PATH (when required), which is why the environment modules enabling different versions of Intel compilers should also modify the environment variable PATH to target to the recent versions of the tools. Unfortunately, the PGI compiler does not currently (August 2018) allow for the change of the GCC used so easily, so the system administrators need to make sure that they configure it against a recent version of GCC during the installation.

⁷ <https://gcc.gnu.org/onlinedocs/gcc/Spec-Files.html>

⁸ <https://software.intel.com/en-us/node/522780>

g) Support and software development tools

ESMs are complex codes running on complex HPC clusters. To make the models use the machines efficiently we need:

- **Support team:** A qualified group of engineers with deep knowledge in hardware and software (including knowledge in applications) with a flexible and fast communication strategy to address and solve user issues. To build such a team requires training and careful recruitment from the management of HPC facilities.
- **Development tools:** to find and solve issues related with code execution, users need specific tools to profile and assess code performance. In the frame of this WP, a strong collaboration has been established with ARM to deploy and use ARM tools⁹. This effort does not only include deployment of the tools on-site but also training and feedback on requirements.

h) Hardware considerations

In this last subsection, we will gather a list of different recommendations that do not fit in one of the prior sections. These are more generic suggestions gathered from different users and system administrators during the project.

When considering architectures, x86_64 compliancy helps (also with AMD but not IBM and ARM). Indeed, trying to build from source a package with many dependencies can be a hard task to do for one of these less common technologies. Usually the community of users is smaller and has less knowledge when reporting a bug; compilers are not so well tuned and tested. To fix and deploy tools on such architectures can be tricky (current experience of BSC using an IBM Power9 machine). This is the case for precompiled binaries which are only built in the most well-known and distributed versions.

Reproducibility of results is also important. How can scientists produce reliable science using HPC if results cannot be reproduced due to hardware or software changes? That is why we need stable environments for the duration of projects, with bit-comparable results, or revalidation. This implies to avoid changing sensitive configurations of the machine or saving part of the infrastructure when replacing a cluster. To tackle this complex issue, containerisation is starting to be used to deploy ESMs, but this topic is not in the scope of this project.

i) Libraries

Many of the problems encountered when deploying an ESM are related to libraries. Dealing with the different source codes, versions, compilers and architectures can be quite cumbersome. This is the reason we strongly recommend to use an automatic (and reproducible) installation system.

⁹ <https://www.arm.com/products/development-tools/hpc-tools/allinea-studio>

To address these common and repeated issues we have put our efforts into the development of recommendations and procedures that help to overcome them and reduce the time to deploy and run a model. The following section of the document deals with this issue.

3. Automating software installation

Getting an ESM workflow to work in an arbitrary supercomputing environment can be tricky. Workflows usually require many pieces of software to be correctly compiled and linked. Many software dependencies have to be accounted for. There are many versions and configuration options for each application, libraries and several compilers that users might want to use (e.g. to find out which one works best for their needs). All this produces a large combinatorial space to get lost in very easily. Many Linux distributions offer their users various package managers that help handle these issues.

Using such managers, users can install software they need without diving into details of software dependencies, configuration and compilation. The problem with those package managers is that usually they are designed to work in a particular well-defined and well-tested software environment (usually with a single compiler and root privileges). Such circumstances are unfortunately not available on most supercomputers.

One of the main goals of this document is to deliver a method to deploy the whole software stack and to automate this process for an arbitrary environment as much as possible. To achieve that we have tested several package managers addressing these issues and accounting for the heterogeneity of HPC systems mentioned above.

a) EasyBuild (package manager)

Based on previous BSC experience, the EasyBuild¹⁰ package manager developed at Ghent University (Belgium) has been selected at first as software to automate software installation. EasyBuild, presented at Supercomputing 2012, has been developed and improved over several years. It has been available on GitHub since April 2012. Today, rather than being developed just at Ghent University, it has become a community driven project. As a mature and tested tool for building software it has been chosen to become part of the OpenHPC¹¹ project.

EasyBuild provides a way for compiling with the standard building tools, like autotools¹² or CMake¹³, but also the possibility to create custom ones. The specific piece of code that allows compiling software is called, in EasyBuild terminology, easyblock. Currently available easyblocks include a set of generic building blocks like configuremake.py, jar.py, or cmake.py. The

¹⁰ <https://easybuilders.github.io/easybuild/>

¹¹ <http://www.openhpc.community/>

¹² https://www.gnu.org/software/automake/manual/html_node/Autotools-Introduction.html

¹³ <https://cmake.org/>

software can be extended easily to provide new blocks to build complex software like WRF (wrf.py).

Our experience with EasyBuild showed that even though it is a great tool, two main issues encouraged us to explore other solutions:

- The tool mainly targets system administrators of the HPC facilities who build software stacks for their system from scratch. The scenario when a regular user needs to extend or upgrade an existing software stack is not well covered.
- The learning curve of EasyBuild is quite steep and it takes time for a developer to start implementing new recipes for packages.

b) Spack (package manager)

Having in mind the problems that we had encountered with EasyBuild, we started looking for alternatives. Our current recommendation is Spack¹⁴ – a package manager designed to be used on different supercomputers for software stack maintenance by users. We chose this software over other existing solutions for its flexibility and comprehensible structure of the code. The latter helped us to adjust Spack to the needs of the climate modelling community and enable automatic installation of most of the packages described in the previous section.

Spack also supports the standard building systems like autotools and CMake. Custom installation scripts can be handled by implementing wrappers (packages in Spack notation) using Python. The installation procedure for Spack is quite simple and described in the documentation that is available on its homepage.

c) Developments

The selection of the tools to be ported to Spack has been done within the project. All the tools ported have been accepted by the Spack developers. To avoid issues with the users, an extensive automatic testing process is done before releasing a package. The work necessary to start a new package from scratch is significant. There are packages (like cdo) with more than ten dependencies in the building stage, and the procedure deployed needs to handle all of them.

To the date (August 2018), the following packages have been made available through Spack in the framework of the ESIWACE project and are available through Spack's main repository¹⁵:

- cdo: CDO is a collection of command line operators to manipulate and analyse climate and NWP model data¹⁶.

¹⁴ <http://spack.readthedocs.io/en/latest>

¹⁵ <https://github.com/spack/spack>

¹⁶ <https://code.mpimet.mpg.de/projects/cdo/>

- cmor: Climate Model Output Rewriter is used to produce CF-compliant netCDF files. The structure of the files created by the library and the metadata they contain fulfil the requirements of many of the climate community's standard model experiments.¹⁷
- Uuid: OSSP uuid is a ISO-C:1999 application programming interface (API) and corresponding command line interface (CLI) for the generation of DCE 1.1, ISO/IEC 11578:1996 and RFC 4122 compliant Universally Unique Identifier (UUID).¹⁸
- grib-api: the ECMWF GRIB API is an application program interface accessible from C, FORTRAN and Python programs developed for encoding and decoding WMO FM-92 GRIB edition 1 and edition 2 messages.¹⁹
- libemos: the Interpolation library (EMOSLIB) includes interpolation software and BUFR & CREX encoding/decoding routines.²⁰
- magics: ECMWF's Meteorological plotting software MAGICS has been completely redesigned in C++. It is intended to be as backwards-compatible as possible with the Fortran interface.²¹
- ncl: an interpreted language designed specifically for scientific data analysis and visualisation. It supports NetCDF 3/4, GRIB 1/2, HDF 4/5, HDF-EOD 2/5, shapefile, ASCII, binary. Numerous analysis functions are built-in.²²
- libaec: provides fast lossless compression of 1 up to 32 bit wide signed or unsigned integers (samples). It implements the Golomb-Rice compression method under the BSD license and includes a free drop-in replacement for the SZIP library.²³

Some other packages like harfbuzz, pango, qt, libtiff, pixman, fontconfig, elfutils, libjpeg-turbo, openjpeg, serf, gmp, gdbm, python, swig, sqlite, py-netcdf, netcdf-fortran, hdf5, libzip, environment-modules, extrae, paraver, openblas, netlib-lapack, eccodes, cmake and libtool have been updated. Information on the packages can be retrieved by running the command: `spack info <name-of-the-package>`.

Finally, eleven system level updates and about a dozen of discussions with the core development team (using git issues) have been introduced in the source code of the tool.

To have a complete list of these developments, browse the code repository²⁴ looking for interactions done by users [skosukhin](#) and [kserradell](#).

On top of that, several contributions were made directly to the repositories of CMake²⁵ and LAPACK²⁶ to enable better support for Intel and NAG compilers.

¹⁷ <https://cmor.llnl.gov/>

¹⁸ <http://www.ossfp.org/pkg/lib/uuid>

¹⁹ <https://confluence.ecmwf.int/display/GRIB/Home>

²⁰ <https://confluence.ecmwf.int/display/EMOS/Emoslib>

²¹ <https://confluence.ecmwf.int/display/MAGP/Magics>

²² <https://www.ncl.ucar.edu>

²³ <https://gitlab.dkrz.de/k202009/libaec>

²⁴ <https://github.com/spack/spack>

²⁵ <https://gitlab.kitware.com/cmake/cmake>

²⁶ <https://github.com/Reference-LAPACK/lapack>

d) Libraries and utilities

As a general recommendation, we recommend to use default and therefore, tuned versions of the more usual libraries for computation. This includes LAPACK, BLAS, FFTW... among others (and their equivalent in other compilers, i.e. MKL). These libraries have been deployed by system administrators in collaboration with machine vendors to get the best performance possible from the machine. A (probably non-comprehensive) list of such libraries is provided here:

NetCDF

Description: NetCDF (network Common Data Form) is a set of interfaces for array-oriented data access and a freely-distributed collection of data access libraries for C, Fortran, C++, Java, and other languages. The NetCDF libraries support a machine-independent format for representing scientific data. Together, the interfaces, libraries, and format support the creation, access, and sharing of scientific data.

Homepage: <http://www.unidata.ucar.edu/software/netcdf/>

NetCDF-C

Description: C interface to the NetCDF library.

Required version: 4.2 or newer

Dependencies: hdf5

Known issues: NetCDF library 4.4.0 or earlier, combined with libhdf5 1.10.0 or greater, will generate NetCDF-4 format files that cannot be read by software using earlier versions of libhdf5 (1.8.x), regardless of the version of NetCDF.

Building system: Autotools or CMake

Mandatory configure options: enable-netcdf4

Name in Spack repository: netcdf

NetCDF-Fortran

Description: Fortran interface to the NetCDF library.

Required version: 4.4.3 or newer

Dependencies: NetCDF-C

Building system: Autotools or CMake

Name in Spack repository: netcdf-fortran

NetCDF-CXX

Description: Legacy C++ interface to the NetCDF library.

Required version: 4.2 or newer in this branch (NetCDF-CXX4 is not backwards compatible).

Dependencies: NetCDF-C

Building system: Autotools

Known issues: This version of the NetCDF C++ library includes no changes since the 4.1.3 release, but is provided for backwards compatibility as a separate package. It was developed before key C++ concepts such as templates, namespaces, and exceptions were widely supported. It is not recommended for new projects, but it still works. A newer version is available, but not necessary for the configurations considered here.

Name in Spack repository: netcdf-cxx

HDF5

Description: Data model, library, and file format for storing and managing data. It supports an unlimited variety of data types, and is designed for flexible and efficient I/O and for high volume and complex data.

Homepage: <https://support.hdfgroup.org/HDF5/>

Required version: 1.8.12 or newer in this branch (see known issues for NetCDF-C)

Dependencies: szip

Building system: Autotools

Name in Spack repository: hdf5

Python

Description: General-purpose, interpreted programming language.

Required version: 2.7 or newer in this branch.

Homepage: <http://python.org>

Name in Spack repository: python

Jinja2

Description: Jinja2 is a template engine written in pure Python.

Extension homepage: <http://jinja.pocoo.org/>

Name in Spack repository: py-jinja2

NetCDF4-Python

Description: Python interface to the NetCDF Library.

Extension homepage: <http://unidata.github.io/netcdf4-python/>

Name in Spack repository: py-netcdf

NumPy

Description: NumPy is the fundamental package for scientific computing with Python.

Extension homepage: <http://www.numpy.org/>

Name in Spack repository: py-numpy

CDO

Description: CDO is a collection of command line operators to manipulate and analyse climate and NWP model data.

Homepage: <https://code.zmaw.de/projects/cdo>

Required version: 1.7.2

Dependencies: netcdf, grib-api, hdf5, udunits2

Name in Spack repository: cdo

NCO

Description: The NCO toolkit manipulates and analyses data stored in netCDF-accessible format.

Homepage: <http://nco.sourceforge.net/>

Required version: 4.6.3

Dependencies: netcdf, udunits2, antlr

Name in Spack repository: nco

NCL

Description: NCL is an interpreted language designed specifically for scientific data analysis and visualisation

Homepage: <https://www.ncl.ucar.edu/>

Required version: 6.3.0

Dependencies: netcdf, hdf5, udunits2

Name in Spack repository: ncl

BSC Performance analysis tools

EXTRAE

Description: Extrae is the package devoted to generate tracefiles which can be analysed later by Paraver. Extrae is a tool that uses different interposition mechanisms to inject probes into the target application so as to gather information regarding the application performance.

Homepage: <https://tools.bsc.es/extrae>

Required version: 3.4.1

Dependencies: mpi, dyninst, libunwind, boost, libdwarf, papi, libelf, libxml2, binutils.

Name in Spack repository: extrae

PARAVER

Description: A very powerful performance visualisation and analysis tool based on traces that can be used to analyse any information that expressed on its input trace format.

Homepage: <https://tools.bsc.es/paraver>

Required version: 4.6.2

Dependencies: boost, extrae, wx, wxpropgrid

Name in Spack repository: paraver

e) Known issues

In order to use the Numerical Algorithms Group (NAG) compiler with Spack, it needs to be combined with GCC as a mixed toolchain²⁷. Currently, Spack cannot handle PIC compiler flags for such a combination but the configuration scripts usually know the right ones for GCC. Thus, you can build packages with the NAG compiler instructing Spack not to inject PIC flags explicitly using the following command:

```
$ spack install hdf5~pic ^zlib~pic
```

It is recommended to instruct Spack to build the utilities that are required only for building (e.g. CMake) of other packages with GCC when the main compiler is neither GCC nor Intel. E.g.:

```
$ spack install netcdf-fortran%intel ^cmake%gcc
```

Some packages cannot be compiled with particular compilers. You can exploit their compatibility with GCC. For example, the Cray compiler can't build libxml2, so build it with GCC. E.g.:

```
$ spack install <package-requiring-libxml2>%cce ^libxml2%gcc
```

You can build for a particular processor architecture if you are on a Cray machine (or on any other architecture with, e.g., different front and back end environments) by specifying the target on the command line. E.g.:

```
$ spack install zlib target=ivybridge
```

You can run the following command in order to get a rough list of available packages (Spack is currently missing this feature). E.g.:

```
$ module avail -t 2>&1 | \
grep -Po '^craype-(?!hugepages|network|target|accel|xtpe)(\S*)' | cut -d- -f2-
```

²⁷ https://spack.readthedocs.io/en/latest/getting_started.html#nag

Currently, Spack uses a similar logic to find the environment modules that set compilation targets for Cray compiler wrappers (i.e. cc, CC, and ftn). If the target is not specified on the command line, Spack will compile for the target that is set by the module that is loaded at the beginning of the login session (Spack runs a separate login shell for this, which means that the default target cannot be changed by switching the module right before running Spack). The following command prints the default target:

```
$ spack arch --target
```

The default compilation target on a Cray machine usually corresponds to compute nodes. If the processors of the login nodes (where you are expected to run Spack) and the compute nodes are different, you might experience problems with packages that either run compiled executables at the building stage (e.g. hdf5) or support the building stage of other packages (e.g. pkgconf). A solution to this is to instruct Spack to build the problematic packages for the target that corresponds to the login nodes. For example, if the login nodes have Sandybridge processors and the compute nodes Haswell processors, you can try the following command:

```
$ spack install netcdf-fortran target=haswell ^hdf5 target=sandybridge \  
^cmake target=sandybridge ^pkgconf target=sandybridge
```

See section cross compilation below for more details.

Automatic software installation requires network access to download source codes. Depending on the security restrictions of the HPC system, a cluster may not have direct connection to the internet, thus blocking any download and preventing the usual way of working with these tools. In these cases, we recommend to employ the mirror feature of Spack²⁸.

f) Cross compilation

Spack has a limited support for cross compilation. The default architecture Spack builds for can be retrieved by running the following command:

```
$ spack arch
```

The users can specify the architecture of their choice on the command line:

```
$ spack install zlib arch=linux-debian8-x86_64
```

The value of the parameter arch is a triplet: <platform>-<operating system>-<target>. The latter two elements of the triplet can be also specified individually:

²⁸ <https://spack.readthedocs.io/en/latest/mirrors.html?highlight=mirror#mirrors>

```
$ spack install zlib os=debian8 target=x86_64
```

The values for `os` and `target` correspond to the fields `operating_system` and `target` specified for each compiler in the configuration file `compilers.yaml`²⁹. Based on the values on the command line, Spack filters the compilers that can be used for compilation, chooses one of them to be used for building (accounting for other constraints, e.g. the compiler vendor constraint `%intel` on the command line), and sets up the building environment in accordance to other configuration parameters of the compiler (e.g. environment and modules).

The rest of the cross compilation logic must be implemented either in Spack package recipes, which is rarely done, or in the configuration scripts (i.e. the scripts provided by the developers of the software along with the source code, which are usually implemented with Autotools or CMake) of the packages. Ideally, a configuration script should not try to run (cross) compiled executables or at least it should not fail the whole configuration stage when being unable to do so. The software developers are usually aware of this problem and follow this recommendation. Unfortunately, it is not always possible.

For example, a configuration script based on Autoconf (part of Autotools) would unconditionally compile, link, and run a *simple* program in order to check whether the cross compilation takes place, and if it does, the configuration script would fail reporting that the user needs to specify the argument `--host` if we mean to cross compile. The value for the argument usually must be recognised by the version of the shell script `config.sub` provided in the release tarball of the package. Spack does not do this by default because the logic triggered by the value of this argument is package-specific and often leads to unexpected and unwanted results.

The simple programs that are used for the cross compilation check are the following:

1. The C program in the original formatting:

```
#include <stdio.h>
int
main ()
{
FILE *f = fopen ("conftest.out", "w");
return ferror (f) || fclose (f) != 0;

;
return 0;
}
```

2. The Fortran program in the original formatting:

```
program main
```

²⁹ https://spack.readthedocs.io/en/latest/getting_started.html#compiler-config

```
open(unit=9,file='conftest.out')
close(unit=9)

end
```

Luckily, the programs are *simple*, which leads to false negative results of the cross compilation checks if the processors of the build machine (e.g. a login node of a cluster) and the target machine (e.g. a compute node of a cluster) are similar, thus making it easy to overcome the described, often artificial and redundant, constraint. For example, such situation is common for Cray machines, where we can perform implicit cross compilations of most of the required packages.

Nonetheless, some of the required packages (i.e. hdf5) need to run (cross) compiled executables at the building stage. Again, if the processors of the build machine and the target machine are not significantly different, meaning, in this case, that the target machine can run the code compiled for the build machine, the users can instruct Spack to build a particular package for the architecture of the build machine using the following syntax:

```
$ spack install netcdf-fortran target=haswell ^hdf5 target=sandybridge
```

Another possible solution available at the user level is to avoid the cross compilation at all by running Spack on a compute node (submitting compilation to queues).

Another solution, which is usually available only at the level of a system administrator (i.e. requires root privileges), is to register the binary format³⁰ of the executables that must be run on the target machine when executed on the build machine. This would allow for completely transparent cross compilation.

³⁰ <https://www.kernel.org/doc/html/latest/admin-guide/binfmt-misc.html>

4. Conclusions and Outlook

The ESM community runs a large range of models on a wide variety of computational platforms. While there has been (and continues to be) software convergence in several areas (data formats, for example, the use of common components such as NEMO, XIOS or cdo, or an increased centralisation of data processing capabilities), there remains significant diversity in ESM software. Consequently, maintenance of the ESM environment continues to pose challenges not only to users (who, understandably, may have little interest in these aspects) but also to HPC service providers.

The major problem here is that many pieces of software that are used in the community, and ESMs themselves, are built with various custom utilities. This situation prevents the application of well-established solutions for software deployment and requires individual treatment for each of them. It increases the complexity of the installation procedures dramatically, as well as the time necessary to perform them.

We admit that there might be good reasons for using non-standard building systems but have to warn the community that this issue requires broader discussion and measures to be taken to reduce the existing diversity of the building systems.

In this sense, identification of software components that are common across ESM systems forms a significant area of work essential to the future success of ESM. In particular, improving the efficiency and reducing the complexity of this effort. The advantages of adopting a common software stack with documented and traceable provenance are numerous (reproducible installation, automatic deployment, thus reducing the time to start experiments, among others) and, in conjunction with the module system, this adoption allows for faster development and debugging. Automation of the software stack installation potentially opens earth system modelling to those in the community without access to HPC resources, and simplifies the role of those providing dedicated ESM support.

The work described identifies software common across the ESM community, and suggests a tool – Spack – to install and maintain this software. We also gathered and listed requirements based on feedback from the community, which will give smart clues and improve the service from system administrators to users dealing with ESM.

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